

Structure of motor and non-motor disorders in patients

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Abstract. The clinical picture of parkinsonism is based on a triad of motor symptoms: hypokinesia, rigidity, resting tremor, which are the result of the death of DA neurons in the compact part of the SN, impaired nigrostriatal connections, and insufficiency of dopaminergic transmission in the basal ganglia and other parts of the CNS. However, the pathological process is multisystemic in nature with dysfunction not only of the dopaminergic, but also of other mediator systems, which causes a wide range of non-motor manifestations of the disease (neuropsychic, sensory, autonomic). The range of motor and non-motor manifestations we identified in patients included in the study is typical for this pathology. Within the main clinical manifestations of both PD and SP, various combinations of motor and non-motor symptoms can exist, which, along with the lateralization of clinical manifestations, the rate of progression, and the age of onset, determines the pronounced clinical heterogeneity of the disease.

Keywords: Depression, parkinsonism, tremor, CNS

1 Introduction

Recently, in developed countries, there has been a slight increase in the incidence of PD, which is associated with an increase in the average life expectancy of the population, as well as with an improvement in the diagnostic capabilities of modern medicine. The typical clinical picture of the latter plays a decisive role in the differential diagnosis of PD with cerebrovascular “accompaniment” and true SP. Within the main clinical manifestations of PD, there are various combinations of symptoms, which determines the pronounced phenotypic heterogeneity of the disease [12], which primarily manifests itself in the form of various forms of PD (akinetic-rigid, tremulous, and mixed), as well as differences in the rate of progression, the severity of motor and non-motor symptoms, predominant lateralization of clinical symptoms.

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2 Materials and methods

In order to study the structure and nature of motor and non-motor disorders in patients with various forms of PD at different stages and in patients with SP; 40 patients with PD and SP were studied. This study was conducted on the basis of the Republican Clinical Hospital-1 and TMA Clinic 1. Complaints, anamnesis of the disease, anamnesis of life were collected from all patients, the somatic and neurological status was studied according to generally accepted schemes. Also, all patients were studied using the following scales: the Unified PD Rating Scale (USARS), the Hoehn and Yahr scale modified by Lindvall, the non-motor symptoms of parkinsonism scale, the Beck depression scale, and statistical data processing was carried out.

3 Results and discussion

As a result of the examination of 24 patients with PD, the following indicators of neurological deficit were obtained. Movement disorders were manifested by a combination of hypokinesia and rigidity (100%) with rest tremor (79.7%) and postural instability (48.6%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Movement disorders in patients with PD.

Hypokinesia was manifested by difficulty initiating and slowing down movements, a decrease in the amplitude and speed of performing fast repetitive movements, hypomimia, rare blinking, hypophonia, micrography, acheiroparesis, shortening of the stride length, shuffling gait. Rigidity was characterized by an increase in muscle tone according to the plastic type and was detected during passive stretching of the muscle. Rigidity was expressed in the extremities (mainly in the distal parts) and neck. Resting tremor was presented mainly in the distal extremities and had an asymmetric character. Postural disorders were manifested by instability with active or passive changes in posture, removing the patient from balance, standing on one leg, and in the later stages - spontaneous balance disorders and falls.

Walking disorders were manifested in patients with microbasia and shuffling gait. At the same time, movement disorders in patients with SP were combined with rigidity (92%), as in PD. However, rest tremor was observed less frequently (35%) compared to PD. Postural instability was observed in 43% of cases (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Movement disorders in patients with SP.

Parameters II and III of subscales of SSOD directly correlated with the stage ($p=0.01$) and duration of the disease ($p=0.01$), i.e. the higher the stage and the longer the disease lasts, the more pronounced the movement disorders and the limitation in the daily activity of patients.

The vast majority of patients with PD (84%) had a unilateral onset of the disease with a tremor or a feeling of awkwardness in one hand, less often the disease began with a trembling of one leg (11%), and even more rarely (5%) a bilateral onset was observed in the form of general hypokinesia and rigidity (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The debut of the onset of PD diseases.

In contrast, in patients with SP in 100% of cases there was a bilateral onset of the disease with a feeling of awkwardness in the hands and tremor. In some cases (43%), a tremor of the legs was noted, and in 63% the tremor on the lower extremities was unilateral (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The debut of the onset of SP diseases.

All 100% of patients, according to the NMSQuest questionnaire, had certain non-motor symptoms: autonomic, affective, psychotic, dyssomnic, sensory.

Thus, the most common non-motor symptoms in PD patients included in the study were: delayed bowel movements (85%), fatigue (69%), insomnia (68%), depression (63%), salivation (60%), hyperhidrosis (56%). In patients with SP, salivation (78%), dysphagia (59%), slow emptying (63%), depression (68%), impaired attention (68%), hyperhidrosis (78%) were most often noted (Figure 5).

Figure 5. The frequency of the main non-motor symptoms according to the NMSQuest questionnaire.

The severity of non-motor symptoms on the NMS scale was associated with the stage of Chen and Yaru ($R=0.7$), the severity of the disease according to the III subscale of the PBDP ($p<0.05$), more pronounced non-motor impairments were noted both in patients with PD and SP in advanced stages of the disease.

Thus, in PD and SP, there is a wide range of non-motor symptoms, the severity of which increases with the progression of the disease in parallel with motor disorders, significantly reducing daily activity.

According to the Beck scale, depression was detected in 58% of patients with PD, mild depressive symptoms were noted in 36% of patients with PD, moderate - in 16% of patients with PD, moderate - in 48%. Depression in patients with SP was detected in 68% of cases, with mild depressive symptoms observed in 45% of patients with SP, moderate - in 35% of patients, moderate - in 20%. Severe depression was not detected either in the first or in the second group (Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6. Identified depression according to the Beck scale.

Figure 7. Forms of depression according to the Beck Depression Scale.

The severity of depressive disorders in PD according to the Beck scale correlated with the stage of the disease according to Hoehn and Yahr ($p < 0.05$), but did not depend on the age and duration of the disease.

Thus, the clinical picture of parkinsonism is based on a triad of motor symptoms: hypokinesia, rigidity, resting tremor, which are the result of the death of DA neurons in the compact part of the SN, impaired nigrostriatal connections, and insufficiency of dopaminergic transmission in the basal ganglia and other parts of the CNS. However, the pathological process is multisystemic in nature with dysfunction not only of the dopaminergic, but also of other mediator systems, which causes a wide range of non-motor manifestations of the disease (neuropsychic, sensory, autonomic).

The range of motor and non-motor manifestations we identified in patients included in the study is typical for this pathology [20].

Within the main clinical manifestations of both PD and SP, various combinations of motor and non-motor symptoms can exist, which, along with the lateralization of clinical manifestations, the rate of progression, and the age of onset, determines the pronounced clinical heterogeneity of the disease. According to the accepted classification [19], there are forms of parkinsonism: trembling, akinetic-rigid and mixed.

As a result of our study, it was found that the ARD group of PD patients is characterized by a later age of onset, greater severity of clinical symptoms, especially the severity of postural disorders, and a higher rate of disease progression compared to the TD group.

J.S. et al. (2009), who revealed a greater severity of hypokinesia, rigidity, gait disorders, and postural disorders in a group of patients with predominant akinetic-rigid clinical symptoms [24]. Almost all authors agree that the trembling form of PD, as a special clinical variant of the disease, differs from the akinetic-rigid form in the earlier development of symptoms [49], the slower rate of progression of clinical symptoms [20], and the rarer development of cognitive impairment and depression [37; 47]. There is even an opinion that the described clinical forms of PD may be independent nosological variants of primary parkinsonism [31].

4 Conclusions

The clinical picture of the syndrome of vascular parkinsonism is characterized by the predominance of muscle rigidity and akinetic disorders. In patients with PD, the tremor-rigid form of the disease predominates. When conducting a differential diagnosis of PD and SP, clinical and anamnestic data should be taken into account. As criteria that determine the severity of the pathological process in PD, it is recommended, along with clinical and neurological data, to determine the degree of neuroimmune disorders based on the results of the study of the content of IL-1 β , IL-10 (material of our next publications).

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